

Ethanolamines as Corrosion Inhibitors for Aluminium 3S in Hydrochloric Acid

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Ethanolamine, diethanolamine, triethanolamine have been investigated as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium 3S in hydrochloric acid solutions. The effect of time, inhibitor concentration, hydrochloric acid concentration and temperature has been studied. Polarisation measurements indicate the predominant effect of the inhibitors on the cathode. The behaviour of these inhibitors towards various aluminium alloys has been given.

IN this laboratory aldehydes, ketones, amines, anilines and organic sulfur compounds are being studied as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium alloys. The present paper deals with ethanolamine, diethanolamine and triethanolamine as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium-3S in hydrochloric acid solutions.

Aluminium alloy Indal-3S manufactured by Messrs Indian Aluminium Company was selected for the study in view of its wide-spread use. It has been specified as follows by the manufacturing company :

Indal-3S-half hard, manganese 1.25%, Fe 0.35%, Si 0.35%, Mg 0.12%, Cu, Ca, Ti traces, remainder aluminium equivalent to JS : 737/1955 NS3.

The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as described in our previous publication¹.

The effect of time on inhibitor concentration and inhibitor efficiency was noted. The efficiency of the inhibitors increases with an increase in inhibitor concentration. Steady values of inhibitor efficiency at various concentrations of hydrochloric acid are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TIME ON INHIBITOR EFFICIENCY
Temperature : $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$

Inhibitor and Inhibitor concentration	Loss	%	Loss	%	Loss	%	Loss	%	Loss	%
	mg/dm ²	Effi- ciency	mg/dm ²	Effi- ciency	mg/dm ²	Effi- ciency	mg/dm ²	Effi- ciency	mg/dm ²	Effi- ciency
	0.5N HCl (24 hrs.)		1.0N HCl (180 mins.)		2.0N HCl (30 mins.)		3.0N HCl (10 mins.)		4.0N HCl (3 mins.)	
Nil	1281.0	—	2552.0	—	5538.0	—	4923.0	—	931.3	—
Ethanolamine (34.80 ml/l)	7.0	99.4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ethanolamine (43.50 ml/l)	—	—	68.1	97.3	147.3	97.3	72.7	98.6	27.3	97.0
Diethanolamine (43.5 ml/l)	62.2	95.1	661.0	74.1	278.5	94.7	389.9	92.1	44.3	95.2
Triethanolamine (43.5 ml/l)	260.2	79.7	914.7	64.2	1318.0	76.2	1442.0	70.7	52.7	94.2

Observations

Ethanolamine is an excellent inhibitor for the corrosion of aluminium 3S in hydrochloric acid solutions. In 0.5 N hydrochloric acid upto 9 hours, ethanolamine completely arrests the corrosion of aluminium 3S and for 24 hrs. duration its efficiency is 99.4%. In 1.0 N to 4.0 N hydrochloric acid it affords 95-99% protection to aluminium 3S.

Diethanolamine is a satisfactory inhibitor for aluminium 3S in hydrochloric acid solutions. It affords 93-98% protection to aluminium-3S in 0.5 N hydrochloric acid, upto three hours. In 1.0 N hydrochloric acid, its efficiency falls with the passage of time, whereas, in general, in 2.0 N, 3.0 N and 4.0 N solutions of hydrochloric acid, its efficiency increases with the passage of time.

The performance of triethanolamine is less satisfactory than that of ethanolamine and diethanolamine. Triethanolamine also increases the cathode polarisation considerably. On the addition of triethanolamine the corrosion potential shifts in the positive direction.

The polarisation results given in Fig. 1 indicate

Figure 1. Influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of aluminium 3S in 1.0N hydrochloric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors.

- ethanolamine 43.5 ml/l
- △—△ diethano'amine 43.5 ml/l
- ×—× triethanolamine 43.5 ml/l
- uninhibited 1.0N HCl

the predominantly cathodic action of the inhibitors. Loss in weight data shows that the general order of efficiency is Ethanolamine > Diethanolamine > Triethanolamine. This order is also reflected in the polarisation measurement as the cathode polarisation is increased in this order (Fig 1).

The tafel parameters are given in Table 2. From

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION ENERGIES OF AL-3S IN 1.0N HCl (IN K.CAL/MOLE)

Inhibitors	10 min.	15 min.
Nil	29.11	29.64
Ethanolamine	23.45	25.34
Diethanolamine	26.06	30.41
Triethanolamine	23.71	23.11

the Table 2 it can be seen that in the presence of all the inhibitors, there is considerable increase in cathodic tafel slope indicating the predominantly cathodic action of the inhibitors.

Plots of log surface coverage against log inhibitor concentration indicate that the Freundlich adsorption isotherm is obeyed in the concentration range (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. A plot of log surface coverage against log inhibitor concentration.

	1.0N HCl	2.0N HCl
Ethanolamine	17.40 ml/l—43.50 ml/l	17.40 ml/l—43.50 ml/l
Diethanolamine	4.35 ml/l—43.50 ml/l	8.70 ml/l—43.50 ml/l
Triethanolamine	4.35 ml/l—43.50 ml/l	4.35 ml/l—43.50 ml/l

The performance of the inhibitors in 1.0 N HCl was also investigated in the temperature range 35°-55°. The activation energies of the inhibitors were evaluated from plots of 1/T against log

DESAI & PATEL : ETHANOLAMINES AS CORROSION INHIBITORS FOR ALUMINIUM

corrosion rates (Fig. 3) according to the Arrhenius equation and are given in Table 2.

Figure 3. Arrhenius plots of inhibited and uninhibited corrosion rates in 1.0N HCl.

————— 15 minutes - - - - - 10 minutes

Lower activation energies in the presence of inhibitors indicate that the inhibitors becomes more effective as the temperature rises. Machu⁸ had reported that for powerful inhibitors, the activation energy is lower for inhibited than for uninhibited

reaction. This type of behaviour has been explained by Putilova⁹ as due to an increase in surface area of metal covered by inhibitor molecules as the temperature rises. However, Riggs⁴ suggested that at high coverages, the extent of adsorption is no longer rate determining.

All the three substances act as inhibitors by adsorption of the onium ions over the metal surface. A comparison of the behaviour of the inhibitors with aluminium 2S and 57S is given in Fig. 2. The general order of protectivity is Al-3S > Al-57S > Al-2S.

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References

1. M. N. Desai and S. M. Desai. Second symposium on corrosion inhibitor. Ferrara, 1966, 207.